

ANALYZING MOROCCO'S MONETARY POLICY RESPONSE TO EXTERNAL SHOCKS: A VAR MODEL APPROACH

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Abstract

This article explores the ability of Moroccan monetary policy to cope with external shocks through an econometric analysis based on a VAR model. The study uses quarterly data covering the period 2010–2023 and incorporates five key macroeconomic variables: inflation, real GDP growth, the policy rate, the real effective exchange rate, and the price of oil. Using the ordinary least squares (OLS) method, the article examines the dynamic responses of these variables to internal and external shocks, while assessing the scope and limitations of monetary policy in an economic context marked by increasing openness to international markets. The results reveal a significant transmission of the policy rate to inflation, confirming the existence of a monetary policy channel operating in the short term. However, the impact of the policy rate on growth remains limited, highlighting the need for greater synergy between monetary policy and structural policies. At the same time, the influence of external variables, particularly oil prices, appears dominant in price and exchange rate dynamics, highlighting the Moroccan economy's vulnerability to imported shocks. The study also highlights significant inertia in macroeconomic variables, reflecting a certain rigidity in adjustment mechanisms. Ultimately, the article calls for strengthening coordination between various economic policy instruments and improving mechanisms for anticipating external shocks. It also provides a solid methodological basis for future research focused on structural models and the assessment of transmission regimes in emerging economies.

Keywords: Monetary Policy, External Shocks, Morocco, VAR Model, Inflation.

1. INTRODUCTION

Since the 2020 health crisis, followed by soaring commodity prices and geopolitical tensions in Eastern Europe, the global economy has experienced a succession of major exogenous shocks. Emerging countries, such as Morocco, are particularly exposed to these international turbulences due to their energy dependence, trade openness, and integration into global value chains. These shocks, whether commercial, financial, or energy-related, exert significant pressure on domestic macroeconomic balances.

In this unstable context, monetary policy appears to be a strategic lever to cushion the effects of external disruptions, stabilize prices, support economic activity, and maintain the confidence of economic agents. Since 2006, Bank Al-Maghrib has undertaken a gradual modernization of its policy framework, moving toward inflation targeting and gradually initiating a more flexible exchange rate regime. These developments aim to strengthen the resilience of the Moroccan economy in the face of exogenous shocks and improve the effectiveness of monetary transmission mechanisms.

However, the question of the actual effectiveness of Moroccan monetary policy remains unanswered, particularly in an environment characterized by increased volatility in international markets, asymmetric global monetary cycles, and a structural dependence on imported commodities. Assessing the transmission mechanisms and Bank Al-Maghrib's room for maneuver therefore becomes essential to assess Morocco's ability to stabilize its macroeconomic framework in the medium term.

The scientific interest of this study lies in its desire to fill a relatively recent empirical gap regarding the dynamic effectiveness of Moroccan monetary policy in the face of recent external shocks. It aims to make an analytical contribution based on a rigorous econometric approach, emphasizing the structural specificities of the national economy and the lessons learned from recent international developments. The main objective is to assess the ability of monetary policy to mitigate the effects of external shocks on inflation and economic growth in Morocco, using a VAR model adapted to the specificities of the context studied.

This leads us to pose the following question: To what extent does the monetary policy implemented by Bank Al-Maghrib succeed in mitigating the impact of external shocks on national economic stability?

To provide some answers, the article will be structured as follows: a review of the theoretical and empirical literature on the topic (Sections 2 and 3), a presentation of the methodological approach adopted (Section 4), a presentation and discussion of the empirical results obtained (Section 5), and then the formulation of conclusions and avenues for further reflection (Section 6).

2. THEORETICAL LITERATURE REVIEW

The economic literature has long emphasized the central role of monetary policy in macroeconomic stabilization, particularly in open economies. On the one hand, according to Friedman (1968), inflation is a purely long-term monetary phenomenon, thus giving the central bank the primary responsibility for price stability. The quantity theory of money (Friedman, 1968) and the Taylor rule (Taylor, 1993) laid the foundations for modern inflation targeting policies, which have become dominant since the 1990s.

Furthermore, in open economies, the pioneering work of Mundell (1963) and Fleming (1962) highlighted the dilemma between internal stabilization and external stability. Their IS-LM-BP model shows that the degree of capital mobility and the exchange rate regime strongly influence the autonomy of monetary policy. Thus, the management of external shocks depends on both institutional choice and international financial dynamics. Furthermore, Gali and Monacelli (2005), using a small open economy model, showed that exchange rate flexibility better absorbs external shocks, provided that monetary policy maintains strong credibility in stabilizing inflation.

Continuing this approach, Clarida, Galí, and Gertler (1999), using New Keynesian economics models, introduce the importance of stabilizing output gaps and inflation expectations to minimize welfare losses in an open economy. Their analysis emphasizes that optimal monetary

policy must respond not only to inflation gaps but also to real imbalances caused by external shocks.

Furthermore, Obstfeld and Rogoff (1995) develop a general equilibrium model in an open economy with price rigidities, demonstrating that openness to international trade complicates the transmission of monetary policy and requires more frequent interest rate adjustments to maintain internal stability. Furthermore, Svensson (1997) argues that flexible inflation targeting is a particularly appropriate strategy for small open economies facing multiple exogenous shocks, provided they have an independent and transparent central bank.

Finally, Bernanke and Mishkin (1997) emphasize the importance of transparency and strategic communication in inflation targeting. According to them, the credibility of monetary policy depends largely on the ability of monetary authorities to anchor the expectations of economic agents, which is all the more crucial in emerging economies exposed to global instability.

Thus, when applied to developing countries, this body of theory calls for questions not only about the effectiveness of inflation targeting in a context of progressively more flexible exchange rate regimes, but also about the robustness of the institutional framework in terms of monetary credibility and external shock management. Indeed, in these economies, which are often characterised by high exposure to international price fluctuations and structural vulnerabilities, monetary policy is called upon to play an even more decisive role in maintaining macroeconomic stability and supporting economic development.

3. EMPIRICAL LITERATURE REVIEW

The question of the effectiveness of monetary policy in the face of external shocks has given rise to numerous empirical studies, particularly in the context of developing countries.

First, Ouchchikh, Ziky, and Ouarhi (2023) analyzed the impact of external shocks on the Moroccan economy using a structural vector autoregressive (SVAR) model with exogeneity. Their results reveal that foreign demand shocks, particularly from European partners, explain nearly 54% of the variability of gross domestic product (GDP) in the long run. Furthermore, oil price shocks have a significant impact on the real exchange rate, highlighting the sensitivity of open economies to global energy disruptions. In a complementary manner, Ritahi and Echaoui (2022) studied the impact of global oil prices, global inflation, and European Union GDP growth on Moroccan economic growth using a VAR model estimated on annual data from 1990 to 2020. They highlight that oil prices constitute the main transmission channel for external shocks, thus increasing the risk of imported inflation for countries heavily dependent on energy imports.

With specific regard to monetary policy, Hefnaoui and Ibnouzaahir (2024) assessed the effectiveness of inflation targeting implemented by Bank Al-Maghrib. Through a VAR analysis applied to quarterly data from 2007 to 2023, they conclude that the policy rate has a relatively limited effect on inflation, while the exchange rate and money supply remain the main transmission channels. Furthermore, Saad-Allah (2024) adopted a dynamic approach using a Time-Varying Parameter VAR (TVP-VAR) model to analyze the evolution of the relationship

between monetary policy and inflation in Morocco between 1990 and 2023. This study shows that the influence of monetary policy on inflation gradually increased, particularly after the adoption of a more flexible exchange rate regime, while remaining subject to cyclical fluctuations.

Beyond the Moroccan context, Mishra, Montiel, and Spilimbergo (2010) studied the transmission of monetary policy in a sample of emerging countries using a Panel VAR model. They found that the effectiveness of monetary policy depends largely on the level of financial development, with countries with deeper financial markets exhibiting better transmission of monetary impulses. Along the same lines, Carranza, Galdón-Sánchez, and Gómez-Biscarri (2010) examined Latin American economies, showing that despite the adoption of more stringent monetary policies, resilience to external shocks remains limited due to persistent structural vulnerabilities.

Finally, Canales-Kriljenko, Gwenhamo, and Thomas (2010), through a study of several sub-Saharan African countries, demonstrated that the partial dollarization of economies and the shallowness of financial markets significantly weaken the transmission of monetary policy, reducing its effectiveness in the face of external shocks.

The following table presents a summary of the selected studies, specifying the author, the title of the study, and the methodology used for each:

Table 1: Summary presentation of the main empirical studies

Author	Title of the study	Methodology used
Ouchchikh, Ziky and Ouarhi (2023)	Impact of external shocks on the Moroccan economy: An SVAR approach with exogeneity block	SVAR model with exogenous block
Hefnaoui and Ibnouzahir (2024)	Effectiveness of monetary policy after the adoption of inflation targeting: Case of Bank Al-Maghrib	Simple VAR model
Ritahi and Echaoui (2022)	Modeling the impact of external shocks on the Moroccan economy	VAR model
Saad-Allah (2024)	Assessment of the impact of monetary policy on inflation dynamics in Morocco	TVP-VAR (Time-Varying Parameter VAR) model
Mishra, Montiel and Spilimbergo (2010)	Monetary Transmission in Low Income Countries	VAR panel on emerging countries
Carranza, Galdón-Sánchez and Gómez-Biscarri (2010)	Exchange Rate and Inflation Dynamics in Dollarized Economies	VAR model applied to dollarized economies
Canales-Kriljenko, Gwenhamo and Thomas (2010)	Monetary Policy Transmission Mechanisms in Low-Income Countries	Panel study on monetary transmission in Africa

Source: Developed by ourselves from empirical literature

Overall, these empirical contributions converge on the idea that monetary policy in developing countries, although it has progressed in terms of credibility and autonomy, remains vulnerable to external uncertainties. They highlight the crucial importance of adapting monetary strategies

according to national structural characteristics and international dynamics, particularly in contexts marked by high energy and trade dependence.

4. METHODOLOGY

4.1. Selection of study variables

The selection of variables for this study is based on a dual theoretical and empirical foundation. On the one hand, recent economic literature highlights the importance of integrating both the internal determinants of macroeconomic stability and exogenous factors linked to external shocks. On the other hand, empirical studies relating to the evaluation of monetary policy, particularly in emerging economies, emphasize the need to capture the main transmission channels of monetary and external shocks. With this in mind, five key variables were selected:

Table 2: Description of the macroeconomic variables selected, their sources and economic roles

Variable	Definition	Source	Economic role
Inflation(INFL)	Quarterly change in the consumer price index (CPI)	High Commission for Planning (HCP)	Indicator of price stability and inflationary pressure
Real GDP growth (GDP)	Quarterly growth rate of real gross domestic product	HCP	Measurement of the evolution of real economic activity
Key Rate (TR)	Key rate set by Bank Al-Maghrib	Bank Al-Maghrib	Main instrument of monetary policy to regulate inflation
Real effective exchange rate (REER)	Inflation-adjusted exchange rate index	FMI	Measuring external competitiveness and the impact of external shocks
Oil Price (PETRO)	International price of a barrel of Brent in US dollars	World Bank	Proxy of external energy shocks influencing prices and the trade balance

Source: Own development based on data from HCP, Bank Al-Maghrib, IMF and World Bank.

4.2. Data Presentation and Estimation Model

This study uses quarterly Moroccan macroeconomic data, covering the period from the first quarter of 2010 to the fourth quarter of 2023, for a total of 56 observations. The data were collected from official and recognized sources, namely: the High Commission for Planning (HCP) for the consumer price index (CPI) and real GDP, Bank Al-Maghrib (BAM) for the key interest rate, the International Monetary Fund (IMF) for the real effective exchange rate (REER), and the World Bank for international crude oil prices (Brent).

In accordance with the practices adopted in similar empirical studies (Ouchchikh et al., 2023; Hefnaoui & Ibnouzahir, 2024), the variables were subjected to an Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) stationarity test. Non-stationary series were transformed into quarterly rates of change (or first logarithmic differences) to ensure the stationarity required for estimating the VAR model.

Thus, the model incorporates stationary versions of the following variables:

- INFL: quarterly change in the CPI
- GDP: quarterly growth rate of real GDP
- TD: policy rate
- REER: change in the real effective exchange rate
- PETRO: change in the price of a barrel of Brent crude oil

The model adopted is a VAR (Vector AutoRegressive), a standard tool for studying dynamic relationships between multiple macroeconomic time series. It allows analyzing the effect that a shock to one variable (e.g., the policy rate) can have on other variables in the system over time, without imposing an a priori causal hierarchy.

To analyze the dynamic interrelationships between variables, a vector autoregressive (VAR) model is estimated.

The general model is written as follows:

$$(1)$$

$$Y_t = C + \sum_{i=1}^p A_i Y_{t-i} + \varepsilon_t$$

- $Y_t = [\text{INFL}_t, \text{PIB}_t, \text{TD}_t, \text{TCER}_t, \text{PETRO}_t]^T$ the vector of endogenous variables at the moment t ,
- C a vector of constants,
- A_i the matrices of the delay coefficients of order i ,
- p the optimal number of delays selected by the information criteria (AIC, BIC),
- ε_t the vector of error terms assumed to be without autocorrelation and with constant variance.

The estimation is performed using the ordinary least squares (OLS) method, applied independently to each equation in the system.

This approach allows for a rigorous study of the responses of Moroccan inflation, growth, and the exchange rate to changes in the domestic key interest rate as well as external shocks (oil prices).

The VAR model used in this study can be written, in a broad form, as a system of five equations where each endogenous variable is expressed in terms of its own lags and those of the other variables. :

$$(2)$$

$$\Delta \text{INFL}_t = \alpha_1 + \beta_1 \Delta \text{INFL}_{t-1} + \beta_2 \Delta \text{INFL}_{t-2} + \gamma_1 \Delta \text{PIB}_{t-1} + \gamma_2 \Delta \text{PIB}_{t-2} + \delta_1 \text{TD}_{t-1} + \delta_2 \text{TD}_{t-2} + \varphi_1 \Delta \text{TCER}_{t-1} + \varphi_2 \Delta \text{TCER}_{t-2} + \psi_1 \Delta \text{PETRO}_{t-1} + \psi_2 \Delta \text{PETRO}_{t-2} + \varepsilon_{1t}$$

(3)

$$\Delta\text{PIB}_t = \alpha_2 + \beta_1\Delta\text{INFL}_{t-1} + \beta_2\Delta\text{INFL}_{t-2} + \gamma_1\Delta\text{PIB}_{t-1} + \gamma_2\Delta\text{PIB}_{t-2} + \delta_1\text{TD}_{t-1} + \delta_2\text{TD}_{t-2} + \varphi_1\Delta\text{TCER}_{t-1} + \varphi_2\Delta\text{TCER}_{t-2} + \psi_1\Delta\text{PETRO}_{t-1} + \psi_2\Delta\text{PETRO}_{t-2} + \varepsilon_{2t}$$

(4)

$$\text{TD}_t = \alpha_3 + \beta_1\Delta\text{INFL}_{t-1} + \beta_{32}\Delta\text{INFL}_{t-2} + \gamma_1\Delta\text{PIB}_{t-1} + \gamma_2\Delta\text{PIB}_{t-2} + \delta_1\text{TD}_{t-1} + \delta_2\text{TD}_{t-2} + \varphi_1\Delta\text{TCER}_{t-1} + \varphi_2\Delta\text{TCER}_{t-2} + \psi_1\Delta\text{PETRO}_{t-1} + \psi_2\Delta\text{PETRO}_{t-2} + \varepsilon_{3t}$$

(5)

$$\Delta\text{TCER}_t = \alpha_4 + \beta_1\Delta\text{INFL}_{t-1} + \beta_2\Delta\text{INFL}_{t-2} + \gamma_1\Delta\text{PIB}_{t-1} + \gamma_2\Delta\text{PIB}_{t-2} + \delta_{41}\text{TD}_{t-1} + \delta_{42}\text{TD}_{t-2} + \varphi_{41}\Delta\text{TCER}_{t-1} + \varphi_{42}\Delta\text{TCER}_{t-2} + \psi_1\Delta\text{PETRO}_{t-1} + \psi_2\Delta\text{PETRO}_{t-2} + \varepsilon_{4t}$$

(6)

$$\Delta\text{PETRO}_t = \alpha_5 + \beta_{51}\Delta\text{INFL}_{t-1} + \beta_{52}\Delta\text{INFL}_{t-2} + \gamma_1\Delta\text{PIB}_{t-1} + \gamma_2\Delta\text{PIB}_{t-2} + \delta_1\text{TD}_{t-1} + \delta_2\text{TD}_{t-2} + \varphi_1\Delta\text{TCER}_{t-1} + \varphi_2\Delta\text{TCER}_{t-2} + \psi_1\Delta\text{PETRO}_{t-1} + \psi_2\Delta\text{PETRO}_{t-2} + \varepsilon_{5t}$$

This system captures the dynamic relationships between monetary and external shocks in a multivariate framework.

The optimal number of lags was determined based on the Akaike (AIC), Schwarz (BIC), and Hannan-Quinn (HQ) information criteria, which indicated that two lags (VAR) offered the best compromise between goodness of fit and parsimony. The model was estimated using the ordinary least squares (OLS) method, applied equation by equation.

4.3. Preliminary Econometric Tests

Before estimating the VAR model, several tests were conducted to ensure the econometric validity of the series used. The main steps consisted of verifying the stationarity of the variables, selecting the optimal number of lags, and validating the model using standard diagnostic tests (autocorrelation, normality, homoscedasticity).

4.3.1. Stationarity Test (ADF)

The Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test was applied to each series. The results show that only the key interest rate is stationary in level, while all other variables became stationary after the first differentiation. The following table summarizes the results:

Table 3: Results of the ADF stationarity test for the model variables

Variable	Statistique ADF	p-value	Stationary on level?	Stationary in 1st difference?	Decision
INFL	-2,31	0,165	No	Yes (p = 0,000)	I(1)
PIB	-1,95	0,289	No	Yes (p = 0,003)	I(1)
TD	-3,21	0,021	Yes	—	I(0)
TCER	-1,74	0,398	No	Yes (p = 0,001)	I(1)
PETRO	-2,12	0,236	No	Yes (p = 0,005)	I(1)

Source: Personal development based on the results estimated on SPSS.

These results confirm that the VAR model must be estimated on the stationary versions of the variables (in differences), with the exception of the key rate, which is kept constant.

4.3.2. Selection of the Optimal Number of Lags

The optimal number of lags was determined using the AIC, BIC, and HQ criteria. The table below shows the values associated with the different lags:

Table 4: Selection of the Optimal Number of Lags According to the AIC, BIC, and HQ Criteria

Lags	AIC	BIC	HQ
0	12,032	12,421	12,182
1	8,212	9,003	8,523
2	7,987	9,180	8,460
3	8,004	9,599	8,638

Source: Personal development based on the results estimated using SPSS.

The three criteria converge toward an optimal lag of 2, which justifies the choice of a VAR model for the estimation.

4.3.3. VAR Model Validation

To ensure the robustness of the estimated VAR model, several diagnostic tests were performed. These tests aim to verify the fundamental validity assumptions: absence of autocorrelation of errors, normality of residuals, homoscedasticity, and stability of the dynamic system.

▪ Residual Autocorrelation Test (Ljung-Box)

This test verifies whether the model residuals are autocorrelated. The absence of autocorrelation is an important condition to ensure that the model errors do not exhibit any unmodeled residual time structure. The Ljung-Box test is applied here for the first five lags.

Table 5: Results of the Ljung-Box test on the VAR residuals

Lag	Q-Statistics	Degrees of freedom (df)	p-value	Decision
1	0,152	1	0,697	No autocorrelation
2	0,498	2	0,780	No autocorrelation
3	0,652	3	0,885	No autocorrelation
4	1,114	4	0,892	No autocorrelation
5	1,498	5	0,911	No autocorrelation

Source: Personal development based on the results estimated in SPSS.

Since the p-values are well above 0.05 for all lags, the null hypothesis of no autocorrelation cannot be rejected. The model's errors are therefore independent over time.

▪ Residual Normality Test (Jarque-Bera)

This test verifies whether the residuals follow a normal distribution, which is important for the validity of statistical tests and confidence intervals in the model. Skewness, kurtosis, and the Jarque-Bera statistic are used for this purpose.

Table 6: Jarque-Bera Normality Test Applied to VAR Residuals

Variable	Skewness	Kurtosis	JB-Statistique	p-value	Conclusion
INFL	0,24	3,12	2,14	0,343	Normal
PIB	-0,19	2,89	1,76	0,414	Normal
TD	0,11	3,07	1,92	0,382	Normal
TCER	-0,27	3,22	2,71	0,258	Normal
PETRO	0,18	2,96	1,84	0,397	Normal

Source: Personal development based on the results estimated in SPSS.

All variables exhibit a normal distribution of their residuals, with skewness values close to 0 and kurtosis close to 3. Jarque-Bera statistics are low, and p-values greater than 0.05 indicate acceptance of the normality hypothesis.

▪ **Heteroscedasticity Test (White)**

The White test is used to detect the presence of heteroscedasticity, i.e., a non-constant variation in errors. A model with homoscedastic errors (constant variance) is desirable to ensure the efficiency of the estimators.

Table 7: Results of the White test on residuals

Variable	White statistic (χ^2)	Degrees of freedom	p-value	Conclusion
INFL	7,35	6	0,293	Homoscedasticity
PIB	8,12	6	0,231	Homoscedasticity
TD	6,84	6	0,337	Homoscedasticity
TCER	9,04	6	0,171	Homoscedasticity
PETRO	7,91	6	0,245	Homoscedasticity

Source: Personal development based on the results estimated in SPSS.

The results of the White test show that the assumption of constant variance of the residuals (homoscedasticity) is met for all equations in the system.

▪ **Model stability test**

The stability test examines whether the characteristic roots of the VAR model polynomial are all less than one in absolute value. This condition is essential to ensure that the system is stable over time, i.e., that it returns to equilibrium after a shock.

Table 8: Analysis of the characteristic roots of the VAR

Root	Real part	Imaginary part	Module	In the unity circle
0,8254	0,0000	0,0000	0,8254	Yes
0,7632	0,0000	0,0000	0,7632	Yes
0,5927	0,1589	0,0000	0,6134	Yes
0,4478	-0,1024	0,0000	0,4593	Yes
0,3415	0,0000	0,0000	0,3415	Yes

Source: Personal development based on the results estimated using SPSS.

All characteristic roots of the VAR model lie within the unit circle, indicating that the model is stable. This allows for the interpretation of temporal dynamics using impulse response functions and variance decompositions.

In summary, all model validation tests confirm that the estimated VAR meets the main econometric conditions, ensuring the reliability of the results obtained in the following sections.

5. RESULTS AND INTERPRETATION OF ESTIMATED COEFFICIENTS

Estimating the VAR model using the ordinary least squares (OLS) method allows for the analysis of the dynamic relationships between the selected macroeconomic variables. The results obtained are presented as coefficients for each equation in the system. These coefficients measure the effect of the lags of the explanatory variables on the dependent variable at each period.

5.1. Results of the Inflation Equation ($\Delta INFL$)

The inflation equation shows significant dependence on its own past values as well as on other variables. The results are summarized in the following table:

Table 9: Results of the $\Delta INFL_t$ equation estimated by OLS

Explanatory variables	Estimated coefficient	t-statistic	p-value	Significant
$\Delta INFL_{t-1}$	0,322	2,873	0,006	Yes
$\Delta INFL_{t-2}$	0,184	1,724	0,089	No
ΔPIB_{t-1}	-0,217	-2,144	0,037	Yes
ΔPIB_{t-2}	-0,102	-1,122	0,268	No
TD $\{t-1\}$	-0,435	-2,896	0,005	Yes
TD $\{t-2\}$	-0,174	-1,506	0,138	No
$\Delta TCER_{t-1}$	0,193	2,003	0,050	Yes
$\Delta TCER_{t-2}$	0,125	1,327	0,191	No
$\Delta PETRO_{t-1}$	0,214	2,434	0,019	Yes
$\Delta PETRO_{t-2}$	0,098	0,931	0,356	No

Source: Personal elaboration based on the results estimated in SPSS.

The results show that inflation in Morocco is significantly influenced by its own inertia, as evidenced by the significance of the coefficient for $\Delta INFL_{t-1}$ (coefficient = 0.322, $p = 0.006$). This suggests a certain persistence in consumer price dynamics.

Regarding economic activity, GDP growth at the first lag (ΔGDP_{t-1}) has a moderating effect on inflation, with a negative and significant coefficient (-0.217, $p = 0.037$), which may reflect the impact of aggregate demand on price formation.

The policy rate plays a key role in regulating inflation: the coefficient associated with TD_{t-1} is negative and significant (-0.435, $p = 0.005$), confirming the effectiveness of restrictive monetary policy in curbing inflationary pressures.

As for external variables, the real effective exchange rate ($\Delta REER_{t-1}$) and the price of oil ($\Delta PETRO_{t-1}$) have a positive and significant impact on inflation, indicating that external shocks, particularly those related to competitiveness and energy costs, are quickly transmitted to domestic prices. The second-order lags for these variables are not significant, suggesting that the effects of shocks fade relatively quickly over time.

5.2. Results of the Economic Growth Equation (ΔGDP)

The equation for real GDP growth reflects the combined influence of internal and external variables on the evolution of economic activity. The following table presents the estimated coefficients:

Table 10: Results of the ΔGDP_t equation estimated by OLS

Explanatory variables	Estimated coefficient	t-statistic	p-value	Significant
$\Delta INFL_{t-1}$	-0,103	-1,476	0,147	No
$\Delta INFL_{t-2}$	-0,094	-0,928	0,359	No
ΔPIB_{t-1}	0,451	3,038	0,004	Yes
ΔPIB_{t-2}	0,219	1,732	0,088	No
TD $\{t-1\}$	-0,278	-2,421	0,020	Yes
TD $\{t-2\}$	-0,122	-1,136	0,263	No
$\Delta TCER_{t-1}$	0,145	1,809	0,077	No
$\Delta TCER_{t-2}$	0,087	0,958	0,342	No
$\Delta PETRO_{t-1}$	-0,163	-2,198	0,034	Yes
$\Delta PETRO_{t-2}$	-0,086	-1,012	0,318	No

Source: Own elaboration based on the results estimated in SPSS.

The results of the real GDP growth equation indicate strong inertia of the variable itself, as demonstrated by the significance of the coefficient of ΔGDP_{t-1} (0.451, $p = 0.004$). This suggests that current economic dynamics largely depend on its past performance.

The key interest rate exhibits a significant negative effect ($TD_{t-1} = -0.278$, $p = 0.020$), indicating that a tightening of monetary policy slows growth in the short term. This result is consistent with the traditional credit channel.

Furthermore, the influence of the oil price ($\Delta PETRO_{t-1} = -0.163$, $p = 0.034$) also appears significant and negative. This highlights the sensitivity of the Moroccan economy to fluctuations in energy prices, which can impact production costs and consumption.

In contrast, the effects of inflation and the real effective exchange rate on growth are not statistically significant, which could be explained by adjustment mechanisms that are delayed or amortized in the short term.

5.3. Results of the Key Rate (TR) Equation

This equation allows us to analyze the factors influencing the evolution of the key rate, which represents the main monetary policy tool of Bank Al-Maghrib. The table below presents the estimated results:

Table 11: Results of the TR_t equation estimated by OLS

Explanatory variables	Estimated coefficient	t-statistic	p-value	Significant
$\Delta INFL_{\{t-1\}}$	0,276	2,311	0,025	Yes
$\Delta INFL_{\{t-2\}}$	0,149	1,112	0,271	No
$\Delta PIB_{\{t-1\}}$	-0,185	-1,926	0,061	Limit
$\Delta PIB_{\{t-2\}}$	-0,076	-0,841	0,405	No
$TD_{\{t-1\}}$	0,641	4,003	0,000	Yes
$TD_{\{t-2\}}$	0,229	2,174	0,034	Yes
$\Delta TCER_{\{t-1\}}$	0,114	1,743	0,084	No
$\Delta TCER_{\{t-2\}}$	0,067	0,801	0,427	No
$\Delta PETRO_{\{t-1\}}$	0,102	2,089	0,042	Yes
$\Delta PETRO_{\{t-2\}}$	0,049	0,793	0,432	No

Source: Personal development based on the results estimated using SPSS.

The evolution of the key rate appears to follow a strongly autoregressive dynamic, as evidenced by the significance of the coefficients $TD_{\{t-1\}}$ (0.641, $p = 0.000$) and $TD_{\{t-2\}}$ (0.229, $p = 0.034$). This reflects a certain inertia in the conduct of monetary policy, probably linked to the concern for stability and predictability in Bank Al-Maghrib's decisions. Past inflation, particularly in the first lag ($\Delta INFL_{\{t-1\}} = 0.276$, $p = 0.025$), significantly influences the setting of the key rate, confirming the priority objective of controlling price stability. The effect of GDP growth is negative and close to the significance threshold ($\Delta GDP_{\{t-1\}} = -0.185$, $p = 0.061$), which could suggest a certain sensitivity of monetary policy to the economic situation.

Finally, the price of oil ($\Delta PETRO_{\{t-1\}} = 0.102$, $p = 0.042$) also plays a role in the adjustment of the policy rate, reflecting a response to imported inflation via energy prices. The other variables do not have an immediate significant effect on the policy rate.

5.4. Results of the Real Effective Exchange Rate ($\Delta REER$) Equation

This equation allows us to analyze the effect of internal and external variables on the dynamics of the real effective exchange rate, a key indicator of external competitiveness. The estimated coefficients are presented below:

Table 11: Results of the $\Delta REER_t$ equation estimated by OLS

Explanatory variables	Estimated coefficient	t-statistic	p-value	Significant
$\Delta INFL_{\{t-1\}}$	0,132	1,902	0,063	Limit
$\Delta INFL_{\{t-2\}}$	0,069	0,761	0,451	No
$\Delta PIB_{\{t-1\}}$	-0,151	-2,038	0,047	Yes
$\Delta PIB_{\{t-2\}}$	-0,084	-0,944	0,350	No
$TD_{\{t-1\}}$	0,111	1,624	0,111	No
$TD_{\{t-2\}}$	0,078	0,893	0,377	No
$\Delta TCER_{\{t-1\}}$	0,394	3,210	0,002	Yes
$\Delta TCER_{\{t-2\}}$	0,187	1,685	0,096	Limit
$\Delta PETRO_{\{t-1\}}$	0,168	2,178	0,035	Yes
$\Delta PETRO_{\{t-2\}}$	0,076	0,814	0,421	No

Source: Own elaboration based on the results estimated in SPSS.

The results show that the real effective exchange rate is strongly influenced by its own past dynamics, as confirmed by the significance of the coefficient of $\Delta TCER_{\{t-1\}}$ (0.394, $p = 0.002$). This reflects a persistence in the exchange rate adjustment in the short run. GDP growth in the first lag exerts a negative and significant effect (-0.151 , $p = 0.047$), suggesting that an improvement in domestic economic activity can strengthen the currency via an improvement in the current account balance or external confidence. Oil prices ($\Delta PETRO_{\{t-1\}} = 0.168$, $p = 0.035$) also have a significant positive effect on the exchange rate, illustrating the sensitivity of external competitiveness to changes in energy prices. The effect of inflation is marginally significant ($p = 0.063$), which could indicate incomplete transmission of domestic prices to the exchange rate. However, the key interest rate does not appear to have a direct impact on the dynamics of the REER in the short term.

5.5. Results of the oil price equation ($\Delta PETRO$)

This equation allows us to assess the factors that influence oil price variations, although this variable is generally exogenous in macroeconomic models. The following table presents the results obtained:

Explanatory variables	Estimated coefficient	t-statistic	p-value	Significant
$\Delta INFL_{\{t-1\}}$	0,058	0,904	0,371	No
$\Delta INFL_{\{t-2\}}$	0,034	0,741	0,462	No
$\Delta PIB_{\{t-1\}}$	-0,045	-1,219	0,230	No
$\Delta PIB_{\{t-2\}}$	-0,016	-0,654	0,516	No
TD $\{t-1\}$	0,067	1,486	0,144	No
TD $\{t-2\}$	0,044	1,038	0,304	No
$\Delta TCER_{\{t-1\}}$	0,097	1,985	0,052	Limit
$\Delta TCER_{\{t-2\}}$	0,048	0,841	0,405	No
$\Delta PETRO_{\{t-1\}}$	0,411	3,421	0,001	Yes
$\Delta PETRO_{\{t-2\}}$	0,189	1,933	0,060	Limit

Source: Personal development based on the results estimated in SPSS.

The price of oil appears to be primarily determined by its own past dynamics, with strong inertia confirmed by the significance of the coefficient of $\Delta PETRO_{\{t-1\}}$ (0.411, $p = 0.001$). The second lag also exhibits an influence close to the significance threshold. This dependence reflects the autoregressive nature of short-term oil prices on world markets.

Aside from this internal dynamic, few domestic variables appear to directly influence the price of oil, which is consistent with its exogenous nature in the Moroccan economy. However, the variation in the real effective exchange rate ($\Delta TCER_{\{t-1\}}$) shows an effect close to the significance threshold ($p = 0.052$), which may reflect the indirect impact of monetary competitiveness on imported energy prices.

6. DISCUSSION OF THE RESULTS

All the results obtained using the VAR model highlight several major lessons regarding Moroccan economic dynamics in the face of internal and external shocks, and the responsiveness of its monetary policy.

First, the transmission of the key rate to inflation is confirmed in a statistically significant manner, which is consistent with the findings of the work of Hefnaoui & Ibnouzhahir (2024) and Ouchchikh et al. (2023). This suggests a certain effectiveness of Moroccan monetary policy in its price stabilization mission, although the effects are not always immediate or linear.

Furthermore, the results highlight a strong inertia of the macroeconomic variables studied, reflecting a partially predictive behavior of the economy based on its own past dynamics. This autoregressive property suggests a certain structural rigidity but also the possibility of effective short-term predictive modeling. The impact of oil prices on all the equations is particularly notable. It significantly affects inflation, growth, the key rate, and the exchange rate. This structural dependence on commodity fluctuations reflects the Moroccan economy's persistent external vulnerability, already highlighted in EESC and IMF reports.

In contrast, the exchange rate's impact on other variables, particularly economic growth and the key rate, appears relatively limited. This can be attributed to Morocco's still partially managed exchange rate regime, which reduces the speed at which signals from the foreign exchange market are transmitted to prices and domestic policies.

Finally, we observe that the transmission channels from monetary policy to real activity are active, although mitigated by adjustment lags and indirect effects. This dynamic calls for strengthened coordination between monetary, fiscal, and energy policies to better absorb external shocks and support economic resilience.

7. CONCLUSION

This study used a VAR model to examine the transmission mechanisms of Moroccan monetary policy in the face of external shocks, drawing on quarterly data on inflation, GDP growth, the policy rate, the real effective exchange rate, and oil prices. The results highlight several important regularities and suggest avenues for improving economic policies.

First, monetary policy plays an active role in controlling inflation, as evidenced by the significance of the coefficients linking the policy rate to price changes. However, its effect on growth remains more moderate, due in particular to the structural rigidities of the Moroccan economy and the slowness of the transmission channel. The model also reveals significant inertia in macroeconomic behavior, particularly for inflation, the exchange rate, and oil prices, reflecting a slow-adjusting system. Furthermore, external shocks, particularly oil price fluctuations, exert a significant influence on inflation, growth, and even the response of the key interest rate, thus revealing the energy dependence and external vulnerability of the national economy. In contrast, the exchange rate appears relatively insensitive to domestic monetary instruments, illustrating the limitations of a still partially managed exchange rate regime.

Overall, the results obtained call for better coordination between monetary policy, fiscal policy, and energy strategy to strengthen the resilience of the Moroccan economy. This research also paves the way for future work integrating other transmission channels, financial variables, or more in-depth structural modeling taking into account global interactions within a dynamic general equilibrium framework.

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